

Time-Varying Correlation between Business Cycle and Financial Cycle in India

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Abstract: The study examines time-varying correlation between business cycle and financial cycle using the DCC-GARCH model for India during the time period January, 2003 to March, 2020. The result of the DCC-GARCH model demonstrates that the time-varying correlation between aforementioned two cycles can be broadly distinguished in three phases. Dynamic correlation between both cycles remains mostly positive with varying degree and exhibits tendency of increase in all phases. The authors believe that an FCI is more effective than a single financial indicator in the central bank's policy decision.

Keywords: DCC-GARCH, Business Cycle, Financial Cycle

JEL Classification Number: C32, E32

1. Introduction

Economic literature has been laden with several research works to gauge the relationship between real and financial sector. Battery of theories and empirical works have assessed this nexus. According to the Schumpeterian theory, the proliferation of financial intermediaries directly affects the rate of technological advancement and productivity growth, which in turn increase the total output. The development of financial intermediaries reduces market friction, boosting domestic savings rates and attracting foreign capital. Thus, the development of financial intermediaries raises capital accumulation and lowers the costs of external financing for firms, which promotes overall economic growth. Several researchers supported the view that financial development is a necessary precursor to achieve high economic growth. The role of the financial sector in shaping the trajectory of real variables in any economy gained revived attention after the 2008 sub-prime crisis. Several researchers estimated the relation between financial development and economic growth. Most showed a positive relationship between financial development and economic growth (e.g., King & Levine, 1993; Levine & Zervos, 1998; Beck & Levine, 2004). Though existing body of literature gauges the relation between real and financial sector, mostly it overlooked the possibility of a non-linear interdependence between them. Later, this asymmetric or non-linear impact of finance on growth (e.g., Deidda & Fattouh, 2002; Huang & Lin, 2009; Law & Singh, 2014) has also been analysed. On the contrary, there are few studies which show negative or weak relation between real

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and financial variables (Naceur and Ghazouani, 2007; Chen et al., 2013). However, it is evident from wide range of research works that the nature of interdependence between real and financial variables is also sensitive to the choice of variables which represent the financial sector of any economy. Financial variable such as domestic credit, broad money, market capitalization, and their respective ratios to gross domestic product (GDP) are typically used to construct a composite index named financial condition index (FCI). The selection of variables is vital for the inclusive characteristic of the representative index.

Growth, the prime concern of economic policy forum, also received fresher attention from theoretical and empirical researchers over time. Though it remains a dominant policy goal, mere GDP growth calculation does not suffice anymore to gauge the overall health of an economy. The latent fluctuation in output's dynamism fosters the notion of the business cycle (BC), an otherwise unobservable phenomenon of output but crucial from a policy perspective. In their seminal work, Burns and Mitchell (1946) proposed the first-ever empirical definition of BC and since then, it has attracted the attention of researchers as well as policymakers. Real BC theorists like Lucas (1976) proposed a conceptual framework to explain the genesis of variability in real variables like output, prices, and employment in any economy. Recent studies show that fluctuations in several financial variables, termed as financial cycles (FC), are instrumental in assessing financial market fundamentals. Variables related to the stock market and money market are also relooked from a fresh financial perspective. This opened a new vista in economic literature where the real economy's relation with the financial market received revised attention, adding a new dimension to age old theme of nexus between 'Wall-street' and 'Main-street'.

The paper analyses the interlinkage between the real-financial sectors in India. The phases of the BC (recession and recovery) and FC (upturns and downturns) have not been investigated in many emerging economies, including India. To the best of our knowledge, limited literature has employed popular DCC-GARCH method to study India's time-varying correlation between BC and FC. Therefore, our paper attempts to fill this gap in the literature. Using principal component analysis (PCA), we have created an FCI, an index which includes broad money, share price, real effective exchange rate, and interest rate (call money rate). The cyclical component of the real and financial index is used to study the relationship dynamics between them. To check the dynamics of a relationship, we have employed Engle's (2002) Dynamic Conditional Correlation-Generalized Autoregressive Conditional Heteroscedasticity (DCC-GARCH) model. We found a positive time-varying correlation between the BC and FC. The remainder of the paper is laid out as follows. Section 2 presents a brief review of the literature, followed by data and methodology in section 3. The empirical findings are reported in section 4, and the conclusion is presented in section 5.

2. Literature review

Several pieces of literature explored the nexus between the real and financial sectors. Financial development indicators are firmly, positively, and robustly correlated with contemporaneous and future economic growth rates (King and Levine, 1993; Levine and Zervos, 1998). Industries that rely on external finance grow relatively quicker in a country with a more significant financial sector (Rajan and Zingales, 1998). Financial development and investment positively impact growth (Khan, 2008). Ghosh and Parab (2019) examined the correlation between money and output for the US, the UK, India, Euro, and Poland. With the addition of divisia money, their study confirms Friedman- Schwartz's hypothesis that money is procyclical. Arcand et al. (2015) identified a finance threshold above which financial development has a negative impact on growth. A similar kind of result is found by Huang and Lin (2009), Cecchetti and Kharroubi (2012) and Law and Singh (2014). Using quarterly data from 1996 to 2018, Kumar and Paramanik (2020) explored the relationship between finance and growth in India. Their findings are consistent with the supply-lead theory, which holds that the development of the financial sector plays a vital role in economic growth. However, a more comprehensive index that considers the impact of financial markets in the mechanism for transmitting monetary policy is now necessary due to growing complexity of global financial system (Swiston, 2008). Hence a literature survey that focused on FCI is critical to explore. Using quarterly data, Giri and Bansod (2019) constructed an FCI for India and investigated its cointegrating relationship with growth. FCI is constructed with the help of PCA, and an autoregressive distributed lag model is used to check long run association between aforementioned variables. They conclude that FCI has predictive power for growth and suggest that it can be helpful for monetary authority in policy decisions. In Indian context, the nexus between BC and FC has been explored by many researchers. Paramanik et al. (2021) examined the nexus between BC, FC, and policy uncertainty in India using monthly data from January 2003 to January 2020. Their findings suggest that BC and FC unidirectionally cause policy uncertainty. Anusha (2015) observed a significant correlation between credit and growth cycles in India and US, with a substantially higher degree of synchronization in US. A brief description of employed data and methodology is presented in the next section.

3. Data and Methodology

We have $Y_t = [Y_{1t}, Y_{2t}]'$, where Y_t is a 2 x 1 vector of BC and FC. The former series is the cyclical component of industrial production (IIP), and the latter series is the cyclical component of FCI. The FCI includes share price, real effective exchange rate, broad money, and interest rate (call money rate). The cyclical component of the weighted average of all these variables is used as a composite financial indicator. The weights are assigned by applying PCA to the above financial variables. All variables have been

deseasonalized using the X-12-ARIMA technique. The cyclical component of IIP is generated using the Hodrick-Prescott (1997) filter, and the frequency parameter $\lambda = 129,600$ is chosen which is in consonance with standard empirical practice and also the definition of the BC (Burns and Mitchell, 1946). Similarly, cyclical component called FC has been extracted. The sample period ranges from January 2003 to March 2020. IIP data has been taken from the Reserve Bank of India (RBI) database, broad money from the Asian Development Bank database, while share price, real effective exchange rate, and interest rate data were obtained from the Federal Reserve Economic Data.

The period from 2003 onwards is chosen because it is considered as "India's dream run," with an average yearly growth rate of around 9 percent until the 2008 financial crisis ruptured it. Between 2003 and 2008, the Indian economy experienced a BC boom. During this time, India's real sector, industry and service sector, telecom service, and software exports grew at around 10 percent per year. The year 2003 marked the pinnacle of national prosperity. Therefore, the study covers both the pre and post-financial crisis periods. However, our study period has not included the Covid and post pandemic period. Since the pandemic has caused severe disruption to both the real and financial sectors, we have limited our sample to the pre-pandemic era.

We have applied Engle's (2002) DCC-GARCH method to examine the BC and FC concordance. A significant feature of the DCC-GARCH process is its capacity to locate changes in the conditional correlation over time and account for the data's time-varying volatility behavior. Furthermore, it can detect negative correlations generated by single-year occurrences, synchronous behavior in stable years, and asynchronous activity during unstable years. The suggested measure does not suffer from "ghost characteristics," as the effects of a shock are not reflected in n successive periods, with n being the window span, unlike rolling windows, which is another technique to capture time variability. Furthermore, there is no need to create a window span or use subsample estimation. The suggested measure does not lose observations.

3.1. DCC-GARCH

The DCC- GARCH model belongs to the class of "Models of conditional variances and correlations". DCC-GARCH model addresses the temporal dynamics of interdependence between two variables. Engle introduced the model in 2002. The primary idea behind the model is to split the covariance matrix (H_t) into conditional standard deviations (D_t) and a correlation matrix (R_t). Both D_t and R_t are time-varying in this case. The conditional mean equation of these two variables can be written in a reduced form VAR framework as:

$$A(L)Y_t = \varepsilon_t, \quad \text{where } \varepsilon_t \sim N(0, H_t) \quad (1)$$

Where L is the lag operator and ε_t is a random error term that follows a normal distribution with zero mean and conditional variance-covariance matrix H_t . H_t can be represented as:

$$H_t = C_t R_t C_t \tag{2}$$

Where C_t is a time-varying diagonal matrix containing conditional standard deviation along principal diagonal:

$$C(t) = \begin{bmatrix} \sigma_{1,t} & & 0 \\ & \dots & \\ 0 & & \sigma_{N,t} \end{bmatrix} \tag{3}$$

and the conditional variance has univariate GARCH (p,q) representation as:

$$\sigma_{i,t}^2 = \alpha_{0,i} + \sum_{q=1}^Q \alpha_{1,i} \varepsilon_{i,t-q}^2 + \sum_{p=1}^P \beta_i \sigma_{i,t-p}^2 \tag{4}$$

R_t is ($N \times N$) conditional correlation matrix, and its specification is represented as:

$$R_t = \text{diag}(Z_t)^{-1/2} Z_t \text{diag}(Z_t)^{-1/2} \tag{5}$$

Where Z_t has GARCH (1, 1) specification.

$$Z_t = (1 - \alpha - \beta) \bar{Z} + \alpha p_{t-1} p'_{t-1} + \beta Z_{t-1} \tag{6}$$

which is a function of α and β two unknown parameters, and the unconditional covariance matrix of standardized residual $p_{i,t} = \frac{\varepsilon_{i,t}}{\sigma_{i,t}}$. \bar{Z} is a time-invariant variance-covariance matrix given by:

$$\bar{Z} = \frac{1}{T} \sum_{t=1}^T \begin{bmatrix} p_{1,t}^2 p_{1,t} p_{2,t} & \dots & \dots & p_{1,t} p_{N,t} \\ p_{2,t} p_{1,t} p_{2,t}^2 & \dots & \dots & p_{2,t} p_{N,t} \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots \\ p_{N,t} p_{1,t} p_{N,t} p_{2,t} & \dots & \dots & p_{N,t}^2 \end{bmatrix} \tag{7}$$

The element of interest in matrix R_t is $\rho_{12,t}$ expressed as- $\rho_{12,t} = \frac{z_{ij,t}}{z_{ii,t} z_{jj,t}}$ and it shows the dynamic conditional correlation between the variable of interest in our case, BC and FC.

4. Empirical results

We have analyzed the macro-finance linkage for India by examining the time-varying correlation between the output gap (BC) and FC. The frequencies are monthly, and the financial index is developed using PCA. Table 1 presents the descriptive statistics of the cycle employed in the study. Table 2 shows the result of the PCA. The first principal component is used to construct the financial index. The procedure to construct the financial index is as follows- Each variable is multiplied by its first principal component, and the sum of the product is used as the financial index.

$$\text{Financial index} = (\text{Call Money Rate} * -0.79) + (\text{M3} * 0.49) + (\text{REER} * 0.35) + (\text{Share price} * 0.08)$$

Table 1: Descriptive statistics

Variable	Obs	Mean	Std. Dev.	Min	Max
BC	207	-1.21e-08	3.033428	-22.01796	7.162144
FC	207	2.22e-08	1.716684	-5.871941	4.912938

Table 2: Principal Components – Loadings and Eigen-values

Variables	PC1	PC2	PC3	PC4
Call Money Rate	-0.79	0.08	-0.02	0.60
M3	0.49	0.60	-0.28	0.55
REER	0.35	-0.73	0.16	0.56
Share price	0.08	0.31	0.94	0.08
Eigen-values	1.35	1.28	0.97	0.39
Proportion of total explained variance	0.34	0.32	0.24	0.10

After the construction of the financial index, the cyclical component is extracted using the Hodrick-Prescott filter. The time-varying correlation between FC and BC is analyzed using the DCC-GARCH model. We have conducted a stationary test and heteroscedasticity test to check the model's validity. To test the stationary of the variable, we rely on Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) test and Kwiatkowski-Phillips-Schmidt-Shin (KPSS) test. The presence of heteroscedasticity is checked by Lagrange Multiplier (LM) test. Table 3 shows the result of the ADF and KPSS tests.

Table 3: Unit Root Test

ADF Test		KPSS test	
Null: There is unit root (Test statistics reported)		Null: Variable is stationary (Test statistics reported)	
FC	BC	FC	BC
-4.43* I(0)	-5.344* I(0)	0.069*I(0)	0.048* I(0)

The ADF and KPSS test result shows that both the variables are stationary at level. The null of the LM test assumes that the series is homoscedastic. We have rejected the null hypothesis of homoscedasticity. All series show the presence of heteroscedasticity; therefore, the pre-estimation test for the GARCH model is fulfilled. The quasi-maximum likelihood estimation methodology is used to estimate the DCC(1,1)-GARCH (1,1) model. The results of the DCC-GARCH model are shown in Table 4. Panel A, B, and C report the conditional mean, conditional variance, and multivariate Portmanteau statistics. The $dccb1$ and $dccb1$, shown as α and β in equation 6 for $m=1$ and $n=1$, are presented in table 4. The theory suggests that β should be positive and significant for validating the DCC model.

In addition, $\alpha + \beta > 0$ is found, with β close to one showing high persistence of the time-varying correlation. We found β close to one for India. Following Ghosh and Parab (2019), we have performed a diagnostics test. A Portmanteau test for residuals of individual variables (Li and Mak, 1994) and cross products (Tse and Tsui, 2002) is done for robustness.

Panel A and B of Table 4 show the conditional mean and variance equation, respectively. A positive and significant value of $dccb1$ is found for India. $\alpha + \beta > 0$ is close to zero supports the validity of DCC (1,1)-GARCH(1,1) model used for analysis. P-value of Portmanteau statistics for residual of individual variables and the residual product is reported in panel C. We found the absence of heteroscedasticity for the variables. In contrast, null hypothesis of the cross-product of residual is rejected. A significant ARCH effect is found for both variables, whereas the GARCH effect is insignificant.

Figure 1 illustrates India's dynamic conditional correlations between BC and FC. The time-varying correlation between the FC and BC is consistently positive over time, and it can be distinguished into three phases. In phase 1 (2003-2009), the correlation between BC and FC is consistently increasing due to high credit growth, a boom in investment, and foreign capital inflows. This period is considered "India's dream run" (Nagraj, 2013) as the growth rate was the highest in the world after China. The growth was led by investment, financed by domestic savings, foreign portfolio investment, and foreign direct investment that was fueled by an unprecedented infusion of foreign private capital. During this period, firms borrowed and inaugurated several projects. In the initial period of phase 1, RBI engaged in sterilized intervention. 2004 is marked as currency trading without being backed by sterilization. The rupee was injected into the economy due to the purchase of dollars without sterilization (Pandey et al., 2019). During the boom, gross fixed capital

formation rose to the level of East Asian economies and bank credit for private housing increased. These fiscal and monetary policies helped the BC and FC to expand.

Table 4: Conditional Mean and Conditional Variance equations

FC (t)	BC(t)	
Panel A: Conditional Mean		
Constant	.03 (.06)	-.05 (.11)
AR(t-1)	.83* (.04)	
AR (t-2)		.65 (.05)
Panel B: Conditional Variance		
Constant	.53* (.18)	1.50* (.38)
α (1)	.24** (.12)	1.33* (.24)
β (1)	.26 (.19)	.08 (.06)
dcca1	.01 (.01)	
dccb1	.98* (.01)	
Panel C: Misspecification Tests		
Portmanteau (Q) statistic (4)	0.24	0.12
Q cross prod (12)	0.01*	

Note: Level of Significance: '*' 1%, '**' 5%, '***' 10%. Std. Err. reported in the parentheses.

Due to the global financial crisis, the correlation between BC and the FC started declining and became negative for some months. In phase 2 (2009-14), the correlation again strengthened due to a coordinated monetary and fiscal policy stimulus package in 2008-09. Growth is restored by liberal credit at low lending rates, increased public spending, and a higher fiscal deficit. RBI to boost investment eases credit and cut rates to increase liquidity. The government cut the tax and increased expenditure in the key sectors to boost demand and production on the fiscal side. To accommodate the stimulus policies, the "Fiscal Responsibility and Budget Management (FRBM) Act" 2003 was suspended in 2009.

The third phase started from 2014 onwards. During this period, the correlation between the real and financial sectors remains stagnant at positive level and decreased later. The Indian

economy began to recover in the third phase, but after the third quarter of 2016-17, this recovery has transformed into a secular fall in growth. Many experts believe that the government's move to demonetize 86 percent of India's currency overnight on November 8, 2016 was the catalyst that sent the country's growth into a downward spiral. Industries, specially medium and small scale suffered most and GDP growth rate slowly plummeted from over 8 percent in FY17 to below 4 percent in FY20. The ripples of demonetization coupled with poorly implemented Good and Services Tax (GST) spread across the economy which was already battling enormous bad loans in the banking system. On the monetary side, RBI started targeting consumer price index (CPI) inflation of 4 percent within a band of +/- 2 percent from August 5, 2016, to March 31, 2021. A decline in the time-varying correlations is observed for India in 2018 due to the home-grown Non-Banking Financial Company (NBFC) crisis. The NBFCs grant loan quicker than banks. Hence, most of the financing was done by the NBFCs, which was stopped due to a liquidity crunch. The automobile sector and real estate companies were getting money mainly from the NBFCs because bank lendings was prohibited in these sectors. The real estate companies were stuck as the projects were not going ahead and shutting down due to the NBFC crisis. It had reduced credit flow and consumption thereby adversely affecting BC.

Figure 1: Dynamic conditional correlations between financial cycle and business cycle

5. Conclusion

The focal point of this paper is to model real and financial linkage in India. In particular, we investigate the nexus between BC and FC. A financial development index is constructed applying PCA technique on four major financial sector variables: real

effective exchange rates, the share price of all shares, broad money, and call money rate. The BC and FC is extracted by applying HP filter on monthly IIP and FCI data. The time-varying correlation between the BC and FC is extracted using the DCC-GARCH model of Engle (2002). The result shows that the dynamic conditional correlation between BC and FC is positive with temporal variation in India. For the period 2003 to 2009, the correlation between BC and FC is consistently increasing due to high credit growth, a boom in investment, and foreign capital inflows. Our estimates show that the correlation between BC and FC has declined post-crisis. The correlation again strengthened due to a coordinated monetary and fiscal policy stimulus package in 2008-09. Growth is restored by liberal credit at low lending rates, increased public spending, and a higher fiscal deficit. RBI to boost investment eases credit and cut rates to increase liquidity. The government cut taxes and increased expenditure in the key sectors to boost demand and production. 2014 onwards, the correlation between the real and financial sectors remained stagnant at positive level and decreased later. A decline in the time-varying correlations is also observed for India in 2018 due to the home-grown NBFC crisis. The authors believe that an FCI is more effective than a single financial indicator in the central bank's policy decision. The central bank of India should create an environment where additional credit can be made available. Along with financial sector reform, the government should improve the efficiency of the financial system. The regulatory authorities should identify which NBFCs are trustworthy so that banks can give good credit lines to lend.

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